

Assessment of Knowledge of Health Care Workers Regarding Occupational Safety and Health in Sporting Students Hospital

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Article History:

Received: 24.07.2025

Revised: 13.08.2025

Accepted: 15.08.2025

Published: 19.08.2025

Abstract

Regarding prevention of occupational injuries and diseases, spreading awareness of occupational safety and health (OSH) is a pivotal factor. Hence, many organizations have executed protocols to raise awareness and knowledge of OSH in the work setting. The aim of this study was to assess the knowledge of health care worker regarding occupational health and safety hazards. This is a cross-sectional study conducted at Sporting Hospital in Alexandria on 100 participants of health care workers. The Collection of Data data was done through a questionnaire which was based on and modified from that of a previous Malaysian study. The questionnaire was reviewed by 2 experts to assess validity. A pilot study was conducted with six healthcare professionals to assess the clarity and reliability of the study tool. The Cronbach test result was 8.2 which is considered a good level of reliability. The questionnaire comprised 10 multiple choice questions divided into the following groups: 2 general OSH questions, 2 OSH legislation, 3 occupational hazards questions and 3 Personal Protective Equipment questions. Statistical analysis was done using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). In this study 100 Healthcare workers have participated. The total knowledge scores among the 100 healthcare staff members showed a mean of 7.18 with a standard deviation of 1.17. In conclusion, the current study was conducted to assess the knowledge of health care worker regarding occupational health and safety hazards. The results demonstrated high knowledge level, with minor gaps in specific procedural or role-based knowledge among the participants.

Keywords: *Healthcare workers, Knowledge, hazard, occupational safety.*

Suggested citation: Hassan, W.Y., Mohamed, M.M., Hussein, R., Gomaa, M.K., & Soliman, H.M.H. (2025). Assessment of Knowledge of Health Care Workers Regarding Occupational Safety and Health in Sporting Students Hospital. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(5), 50-55. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(5\).06](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(5).06)

Introduction

Regarding prevention of occupational injuries and diseases, spreading awareness of occupational safety and health (OSH) is a pivotal factor. Hence, many organizations have executed protocols to raise awareness and

knowledge of OSH in the work setting, among healthcare personnel inclusively, following the validation of the Occupational Safety and Health Act (OSHA) (Lugah, et al., 2010.) Health system staff work in a relatively dangerous setting when compared to other non-medical employees, as they are liable to biohazards (Odonkor, & Sallar, 2024). As reported by the WHO, around 59 million people work in medical field worldwide, around 12% of the labour force is regarded to be one of the most dangerous occupational environments (WHO, 2022).

The WHO also announced that all healthcare personnel, including healthcare professionals, are threatened by occupational risks. Millions of health service staff experience occupational illness and accidents, and many of them die, as stated by the ILO (International Labour Organization) (NIOSH, n.d). Experts are struggling to educate people and spread knowledge regarding the significance of occupational health and safety and the hazards faced by the health service workers (Nyame-Annan, 2017).

Occupational hazard is described as any risk faced by the worker at the workplace and it includes many types: chemical, physical, biological, and psychosocial. It can also be defined as any stuff, incident or circumstance which may cause accident or illness at the work environment (Fasunloro, & Owotade, 2004; Fernandez, et al., 2017). Health system staff are vulnerable to multiple occupational health and safety threats, for example: needle stick prick, carcinogens, musculoskeletal diseases, latex allergies, violence and stress in health care facilities. Over the past few years the scale of occupational injuries among health service personnel has been rising (NIOSH, 2009). In the United States, 17–57 deaths per one million healthcare workers were registered due to

occupational incidents, including infection, according to a study by Sepkowitz and Eisenberg (Sepkowitz, & Eisenberg, 2005).

Nurses are the most vulnerable workers to musculoskeletal disorders when compared to other professions, reaching up to 40-80% among all citizens. According to WHO, the most injured body parts and their prevalence rates are: lower back area with 29- 64%, neck 34%- 54% and shoulders 35-60% (WHO, 2022). According to a study done on biological risks, 97% of healthcare staff had needle stick injury, with 1.9% of the wounded individuals contracted HBV infection (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2022). In Egypt health care staff are threatened by Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) infection and other blood spread microbes. The number of needle stick injuries calculated to be 4.9 per healthcare worker per year and most of HCV infections (66%) are contributed to occupational exposures (Ameen, et al., 2020). Since the 20th century, the wellbeing of health service staff has been an important legal issue in Egypt, Nowadays this concern has grown especially with the vision of the newly applied Constitution of Egypt, which prioritizes health particularly (Zawilla, 2016).

The Aim of This Study was to assess the knowledge of health care worker regarding occupational health and safety hazards.

Materials and Methods

Study Setting

Students Sporting Hospital affiliated to the Health Insurance in Alexandria.

Study Design

A cross-sectional study.

Study Population

HCWs of Students Sporting Hospital.

Inclusion Criteria

HCWs of Students Sporting Hospital who are subjected to hazards.

Exclusion Criteria

Administrative staff.

Sample Size

According to the previous Malaysian study. We considered level of significance as 0.05 and the power of the study was 95%, the appropriate sample size was 92 participants and rose to 100 to compensate for non-response ratio of study subjects. (1)

Sample Type

Simple random sample.

Data Collection

We collected data through a questionnaire which was based on and modified from that of a previous Malaysian study. The questionnaire was reviewed by 2 experts to assess validity. A pilot study was conducted with six healthcare professionals to assess the clarity and reliability of the study tool. The Cronbach test result was 8.2 which is considered good level of reliability. The questionnaire comprised 10 multiple choice questions divided into the following groups: 2 general OSH questions, 2 OSH legislation, 3 occupational hazards questions and 3 Personal Protective Equipment questions

Ethical Considerations

Before conducting the research, we obtained an official approval from IRB of Health Insurance Organization. Participation was voluntary; and anonymity and data confidentiality were strictly maintained. The study subjects signed consents before participation in the study. Data collection started on 14/5/2025 till 30/6/2025.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was done using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Numerical data were expressed as mean and standard deviation or median and range as appropriate. Qualitative data were expressed as frequency and percentage. All tests were two-tailed. Multilinker regression analysis was conducted using the forward method in six steps, examining all demographic variables and all questionnaire items. A p-value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Results

Table 1 demonstrates that the study included 100 healthcare staff members. The median age of participants was 32 years with an interquartile range (IQR) of 28 to 39 years, and an age range from 22 to 59 years. The majority of participants were female (86%), while male participants constituted 15%. Regarding work experience, 56% had less than 10 years of experience, 25% had between 10 and 20 years, and 19% had more than 20 years. In terms of job status, 78% were assigned staff, while contracted (6%), fellowship (10%), and delegated staff (6%) made up the remainder. The job description distribution showed that nurses formed the largest group (44%), followed by physicians (25%), lab technicians (11%), chemists (7%), pharmacists (5%), lab specialists (3%), high nurses (2%), dentists (2%), and biomedical staff (1%). This diverse sample provides a broad representation of healthcare roles within the hospital setting.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Study Population (n=100)

Median age (IQR) MIN-MAX	32(28-39)	Min	22	Max	59
	Category	No	%		
Gender	Male	14	14		
	Female	86	86		
Experience years	Less than 10	56	56		
	From 10 to 20	25	25		
	More than 20	19	19		
Job status	Assigned	78	78		
	Contracted	6	6		
	Fellowship	10	10		
	Delegated	6	6		
Job description	Chemist	7	7		
	Lab specialist	3	3		
	Lab technician	11	11		
	High nurse	2	2		
	nurse	44	44		
	Pharmacist	5	5		
	Physician	25	25		
	Dentist	2	2		
Biomedical staff	1	1			

Table 2. shows the analysis of the knowledge-related questions revealed varying levels of

awareness among healthcare staff. While 58% identified the direct supervisor as the appropriate person to notify in case of a ward incident, 25% selected the safety officer, indicating some confusion in reporting protocols. Similarly, 55% recognized that all staff are responsible for ensuring safety and health in the hospital, while 40% attributed this solely to the safety officer. Regarding legislative responsibility, the majority (78%) identified the Ministry of Health as the authority responsible for occupational safety laws in Egypt. Awareness of safety roles was high, with 66% identifying the safety officer as the head of the occupational

health and safety committee. Most participants demonstrated comprehensive knowledge of occupational hazards, with 94% selecting "all of the above" for general hazards, 99% for hazard types, and 100% for ergonomic risks. Similarly, 100% correctly identified the meaning of personal protective equipment (PPE), and 99% knew when gloves must be worn. However, only 75% identified the N95 mask as the minimum required respiratory protection for airborne diseases, while 20% selected "Q Musk." These findings suggest strong general awareness of occupational safety, with minor gaps in specific procedural or role-based knowledge.

Table 2. Responses to Survey Questions about Knowledge of Occupational Hazards (n= 100)

Questions	Response	N0	%
Who should be notified in case of an incident in the ward?	Direct supervisor	58	58
	Director of Medical Affairs	12	12
	Security Officer	5	5
	Safety Officer	25	25
Who is responsible for ensuring safety and health in the hospital?	All staff	55	55
	Hospital Director	5	5
	Safety Officer	40	40
Which ministry is responsible for implementing occupational health and safety laws in Egypt?	Ministry of Environment	15	15
	Ministry of Health	78	78
	Ministry of Manpower and Migration	7	7
Who is the head of the occupational health and safety committee at the workplace?	Maintenance Engineer	1	1
	Facility Manager	32	32
	Safety Officer	66	66
	Infection Control Officer	1	1
What are the occupational hazards for healthcare workers?	All of the above	94	94
	Needle stick injuries	6	6
What are the types of occupational hazards in the healthcare environment?	All of the above	99	99
	Chemical hazards	1	1
What are the ergonomic hazards (human factor) in the workplace?	All of the above	100	100
What is the minimum required respiratory mask for the case of disease?	Mu2	5	5
	N95	75	75
	Q Musk	20	20
When must gloves be worn?	All of the above	99	99
	When handling chemical materials	1	1
What is Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)?	All of the above	100	100

The total knowledge scores among the 100 healthcare staff members showed a mean of 7.18 with a standard deviation of 1.17. The median score was 7.0, with an interquartile range from 6.0 to 8.0, and the scores ranged from a minimum of 4 to a maximum of 10. The

knowledge level of participants about occupational hazards was categorized based on their total knowledge score out of 10. Since no participant scored below 4, the cut-off points were adjusted to reflect the actual distribution of scores as follows, A score of

4–6 was considered as moderate knowledge, 7–8 as high knowledge, and 9–10 as very high knowledge. It was found that 29 participants were classified as having moderate knowledge, 58 as having high knowledge, and 13 as having very high knowledge as shown in table 3.

Table 3. Total Score of Occupational Hazard Questionnaire in El-Talaba Hospital (n=100)

Total score	No
Mean (Std. Deviation)	7.18 (1.17)
Median (Q3-Q1)	7.0(8.0-6.0)
Minimum	4
Maximum	10
Moderate knowledge	29
High knowledge	58
Very high knowledge	13

Multilinear regression analysis was conducted using the forward method in six steps, examining all demographic variables and all questionnaire items. The final model (Model 6) achieved an R² of 0.775, indicating that approximately 77.5% of the variance in the log-transformed knowledge score could be explained by the included predictors. This reflects a strong explanatory power of the model. The adjusted R², which accounts for the number of predictors, remained high at 0.760, confirming the model's robustness. The ANOVA results further supported the model's statistical significance. Across all models, each regression model significantly improved the prediction of the

dependent variable compared to a model with no predictors. In the final model (Model 6), $F(6, 93) = 53.281, p < .001$, confirming that the set of predictors significantly contributed to explaining variations in knowledge scores.

A multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the factors associated with healthcare staff knowledge about occupational hazards at Sporting Students Hospital (Table 4). The dependent variable was the total knowledge score, which was log-transformed to improve normality. The results showed that several variables were significantly associated with knowledge levels. Specifically, knowledge was significantly lower among respondents who were unaware of who should be notified in case of an incident in the ward ($B = -0.022, p < .001$), who did not know who is responsible for ensuring safety and health in the hospital ($B = -0.031, p < .001$), and who were unfamiliar with the minimum required respiratory mask in cases of airborne diseases ($B = -0.053, p < .001$). Additionally, lack of awareness about occupational hazards in the healthcare environment ($B = -0.094, p < .001$) and about which ministry is responsible for implementing occupational health and safety laws in Egypt ($B = -0.016, p = .014$) were associated with significantly lower knowledge scores. Interestingly, job status was positively associated with knowledge ($B = 0.009, p = .043$), indicating that assigned persons may be linked to higher awareness of occupational safety and health practices.

Table 4. Factors Affecting Knowledge of Sporting Students Hospital Hospital Staff about Occupational Hazards (n=100)

Factors	Unstandardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	
Constant	1.167	0.025	0.000
Who should be notified in case of an incident in the ward?	-0.022	0.003	0.000
Who is responsible for ensuring safety and health in the hospital?	-0.031	0.004	0.000
What is the minimum required respiratory mask for the case of disease?	-0.053	0.007	0.000
What are the types of occupational hazards in the healthcare environment?	-0.094	0.016	0.000
Which ministry is responsible for implementing occupational health and safety laws in Egypt?	-0.016	0.006	0.014
Job status	0.009	0.004	0.043

Discussion

In this study 100 Healthcare workers have participated. More than half of the participants

(58%) choose direct supervisor as the appropriate person to notify in case if there is an incident in the ward, while 25% of participants

choose safety officers which is higher than that of the Malaysian study where 40.5% of the participants selected direct supervisor as the appropriate person to notify in case if there is an incident in the ward (Lugah, et al., 2010). This finding sheds light on the role of supervisors in guiding staff about principles of health and occupational safety in healthcare settings. Furthermore, about half (55%) of the participants realized that all the staff are responsible for ensuring safety and health in the hospital, while 40% selected the safety officer which aligns with the Malaysian study where 58.7% indicated that all the staff is responsible for safety and health (Lugah, et al., 2010).

About one third of the participants recognized that head of the organization is the same head of health and occupational safety committee at the workplace, while 66% chose safety officers. This finding is less than that of the Malaysian study where 45.4% of participants selected the same answer. The total knowledge score of the participants was 7.18 which reflected very good level of knowledge and is higher than that of the Malaysian study where the overall level of knowledge was moderate with a percentage mean score 62%. This result implied the significant attention of the health care authority in Egypt toward the OSH educational programs for staff. The current study provides valuable data regarding the culture of staff regarding health and occupational safety. However, the study had a limitation that it was conducted at governmental hospital so the sample did not include representatives from the private sector which could affect the external validity of the study.

Conclusion

The current study was conducted to assess the knowledge of health care worker regarding occupational health and safety hazards. The results demonstrated high knowledge level, with minor gaps in specific procedural or role-based knowledge among the participants. Additionally, lack of awareness about occupational hazards in the healthcare environment and about which ministry is responsible for implementing occupational health and safety laws in Egypt were associated with significantly lower

knowledge scores. This finding implied the need for conducting continuous professional programs for HCWs regarding health and occupational safety to enhance their knowledge.

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